

Review

Extensive use of organochlorine pesticides in agriculture: environmental and health concerns: A review

Muhammad Hafeez^{1*}, Sakhawat Shah², Xiaowei Li¹, Zhijun Zhang¹, Jun Huang¹, Likun Wang¹, Asim Gulzar³, Ehsan Ali², Bahar Ali², Yaobin Lu^{1*}

¹State Key Laboratory Breeding Base for Zhejiang Sustainable Pest and Disease Control, Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Institute of Plant Protection and Microbiology, Hangzhou 310021, P.R.Ch

²Hubei Insect Resources Utilization and Sustainable Pest Management Key Laboratory, College of Plant Science and Technology, Huazhong Agricultural University, Wuhan 430070, Hubei, China

³Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi Shamsabad, Pakistan

*Corresponding authors

1. Muhammad Hafeez, hafeez_203@yahoo.com

2. Prof. Yaobin Lu, luybcn@163.com

Accepted: 1 March, 2020; Online: 27 March, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3728264>

Abstract : Pesticides are widely used in agriculture mainly to increase crop yields cater to huge supply of food products for increasing world population as well as to protect crops from pests and control insect-borne diseases. Increased use of pesticides (especially organochlorine pesticides) results in contamination of the environment and the excess accumulation of pesticide residues in food products and severe health impact, which has always been a matter of serious concern. Pesticide residues in food and crops are directly related to the irrational application of pesticides to the growing crops. Accumulated organochlorine pesticide residues in food products have been associated with a broad variety of human health hazards, ranging from short-term effects to long-term toxic effects. The preventive measures for pesticide residues in the developing countries are limited due to a shortage of funds and lack of defined government regulations. The impact of pesticide residues can be minimized by taking certain measures such as the rational use of pesticides, promoting organic farming, exploit natural and bio pesticides, and proper implementation and amendment of pesticide-related laws. The present article has been planned to review various aspects of organochlorine pesticide residues including their accumulation in air, soil, water and food products, impact on human health, and the preventive measures to counter their toxic effects.

Keywords: Agriculture; OC pesticides residues; Hazards; Human health; Environment.

Introduction:

The agriculture sector is the largest consumer of pesticides (about 85% of the world's production), use of pesticides has offered significant economic benefits by enhancing the production and yield of food and fibres and to control of various pests. In addition, pesticides are also used in public health activities to control the spread of vectors borne diseases (such as malaria and dengue) and the unwanted plants (for example, grass And weeds), in the landscaping, parks and gardens. They are also helpful to inhibit or prevent the spread of insect's pests, bacteria, fungi, and algae in refrigerators electronic devices, Paints, carpets, paper, cardboard and food packaging materials (Gilden et al., 2010). Pesticides are one of the few and most important toxic substances released deliberately into the environment to kill unwanted organism. Though the term pesticide is often misunderstood to refer only to insecticides, it is also applicable to herbicides, fungicides, and various other substances used to control unwanted pests' (Matthews, 2006). Organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) belongs to the class of hydrocarbons characterize by its cyclic structure, most of the organochlorine pesticides (e.g., aldrin, chlordane, dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), dieldrin, endrin, heptachlor, and hex-chlorobenzene) contain persistent organic pollutants (POPs) that resist degradation and thus remain in the environment for many years (Sharma et al., 2015; Yadav et al., 2015). In addition, these compounds have the potential to accumulate potentially and biomagnify, they can be bio-concentrated 7 million times relative to its initial concentration (Hernández et al., 2013). Repeated application of pesticides leads to the loss of biodiversity and increased resistance of pests, and its effect on other species contributes to the resurgence of pests (Damalas and Eleftherohorinos, 2011). It is estimated that > 95% application of pesticides may affect non-target organisms and become widely dispersed in the environment (Simeonov et al. 2013) like soil (Kumar et al., 2014), air (Devi et al., 2011), water (Lari et al., 2014) and food (Yu et al., 2012). Similar to other chronic organic contaminants like polychlorinated biphenyls, and polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins/furans (PCDDs/Fs) when these chlorinated compounds are introduced in the environment they are distributed very slowly and gradually and become the part of the air, soil, water and persist in living organisms. OCPs are capable of spreading over long distances through atmospheric movement along with human and animal activities. Even large flocks of migratory birds can be a considerable contribution to the spread of these environmental pollutants (Alcock et al., 2008)

However, unintended exposure to pesticides can be extremely dangerous to humans and other organisms because they are designed to be poisonous (Sarwar, 2015). Organochlorine pesticides were extensively used in agriculture throughout the world between 1950 and 1970 (Li and Macdonald, 2005). In recent years, OCPs have attracted worldwide concern for decades because of their long half-lives and potential adverse effects on human health (Androutsopoulos et al. 2013). Most of OCPs were banned for use in the 1970s in many countries, but many developing countries continue using them in the agricultural industry and for malaria control due to their low-cost and effectiveness, because of extensive application they have been detected in maternal blood (Qu et al., 2010), and even umbilical cord blood (Yu et al. 2013) and placenta (Ren et al., 2011), human breast milk (Parsehian, 2008), OCPs can be absorbed into an organism's body through the skin, respiration or if ingested, can be absorbed through the gut wall. Susceptibility to absorption is not consistent across all OCPs with Cyclodienes, hexachlorocyclohexane, endosulfan and lindane passing more freely across the skin barrier than compounds like dicofol, toxaphene, DDT, mirex and methoxychlor (Amdur et al., 1992). OCPs are quickly consumed in the small intestinal tract and utilise the circulatory system to spread across the body and accumulate in human cells with high-fat contents, with a constant exchange occurring between veins and cells. As such, these chemicals are detectable in vein cells (whole veins, cord veins, serum and plasma), adipose cells (identified through autopsies and living subjects), muscles, hair, breast milk (Tsatsakis and Tutudaki, 2008; Jakszyn et al. 2009; Tsang et al., 2011; Appenzeller and Tsatsakis, 2012; Mrema et al., 2013) Epidemiological documentation show increases in occurrence and incidence of diseases related with endocrine-disrupting chemicals, such as breast and prostate cancer, obesity, diabetes, and a decline in fertility in the last 50 years (Coster and van Larebeke, 2012). The present work has been planned to review various aspects of organochlorine pesticide residues including accumulation of pesticide residues in food grains, environmental and various hazards to human health due to pesticide residues as well as preventive measures for the minimization of the impact of organochlorine pesticide residues on human health.

Organochlorine pesticide use in agro-system

The basic advantages of OCPs usage to get a higher outcome from produce. Improving food production efficiency is one of the greatest concerns the world currently faces. With the human population predicted to grow to nearly 10 billion by 2050 we will need to develop effective and sustainable approaches to feeding the next generation of inhabitants. Current evidence suggests an

increase of approximately 97 million per year (Margni et al. 2002). The UN's Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) has released a startling prediction that global food production needs to increase by 70%, to keep speed with the demand of the growing population. However, creating a tremendous increase in food manufacturing is replete with difficulties especially given the limited land area available for expansion of agriculture (Saeedi Saravi and Dehpour, 2016). The importance of pesticides for the most developing nations around the world is proven. Efforts to increase food production capacity are stimulated by the great number of challenges we currently face, such as world population expected to exceed 10 billion by 2050 creating a drastically decreased ratio of arable land to population (Shokrzadeh and Saravi, 2009; Saeedi Saravi and Dehpour, 2016). The use of chemical pesticides has provided valuable aid to agricultural production, increasing crop protection and yield. However, the discovery of pesticide residues in various sections of the environment has raised serious concerns regarding their use; concerns which will outweigh the overall benefits derived from them (Ali et al., 2014; Sharma et al., 2014). Organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) have been in wide usage across the world to control agricultural pests and vector-borne diseases (Abhilash and Singh 2009; Zhang et al., 2011). Amongst the OCPs in regular usage, dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH), endosulfan, aldrin, chlordane, dieldrin, endrin, heptachlor, mirex, hexachlorobenzene (HCB) and toxaphene, methoxychlor, and metolachlor are persistent organic pesticides. OCPs are very stable compounds and their half-lives can range from a few months to several years; in some cases decades (Cremllyn, 1991). It has been estimated that the degradation of DDT in soil ranges from 4 to 30 years, while other chlorinated OCPs may remain stable for many years after their use (Afful and Anim, 2010). Because of their inability to break down in the environment, their degradation is restricted by chemical, physical, biological and microbiological means (Swackhamer and Hites 1988; Darko and Acquah, 2007; Afful and Anim, 2010; Centers for disease control and prevention (CDC) 2017). **Figure 1.** They are liposoluble compounds and are capable of bioaccumulating in the fatty parts of biota such as breast milk, blood and fatty tissues (Ntow et al., 2008) in the food chain. As a result, human beings are exposed to the effects of these micropollutants by eating foods in contact with contaminated soil or water (Belta et al., 2006; Júnior and Ré-Poppi, 2007). The overuse of these pesticides not only cause contaminate the environmental also cause the serious diseases in humans and also highly toxic to most aquatic life (Aiyesanmi et al., 2012) and soil microflora (Megharaj, 2002). The side effects due the exposure

to OCPs is dependent on the type used and mode of inducing pest mortality, level of exposure and length of exposure is also critical. Exposure in the environment then allows the pesticides to enter the body through the four major tracks, such as breathing, skin, dental, and ocular (Shokrzadeh and Saravi, 2009)

Fig. 1 Overview of organochlorine pesticides use and impact on Agriculture and Public health

Organochlorine pesticides OCPs, chemistry, toxicity and persistence in the environment

The basic physical characteristics of organochlorine pesticides are high persistence, low polarity, low aqueous solubility and high lipid solubility. Organochlorine pesticides can come in the environment after pesticide applications, polluted wastes discarded into landfills, and discharges from industrial units that synthesize these chemicals. They are volatile and stable; some can adhere to the soil and air, thus increasing the chances of high persistence in the environment, and are identified as agents of chronic exposure to animals and humans. **Table 1** provides a comprehensive summary of major organochlorine pesticides with their chemical name, structure, toxicity, Chemical type and persistence in the environment. They have a related chemical structure, showing chlorine substituted aliphatic or aromatic rings. Due to their structural resemblances, these compounds share certain physicochemical characteristics such as persistence, bioaccumulation and toxicity. One basic character that they share across the spectrum is persistence, where persistence is defined as half-life greater than two months in water or six months in soil sediment. The persistence of OC compounds varies from moderate persistence with half-life of approximately 60 days to high persistence with half-life up to 10 15 years. The most commonly used pesticide in agricultural practice is dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), which is moderately hazardous, with high persistence and a half-life of 2–15 years (Augustijn-Beckers et al., 1994). The use of DDT is now banned in many countries but it is illegally used in most of the developing countries. This applies also to endosulphan, an insecticide which is highly hazardous and has moderate persistence with a half-life of fifty days and is used in the production of cashew (R. 2002).

Tab. 1 Overview of some major health problem related to organachlorine pesticides (OCPs)

Disease	Pesticides class	Reference
Breast cancer	β -HCH and p,p'-DDE	[(Arrebola et al., 2015)]
	HCB	[(Parada et al., 2016)]
	DDT,DDE, PCB,DDT	[(Randhawa et al., 2015)]
		(Li et al. 2013)
Liver cancer	DDT adjusted for DDE level	[(McGlynn et al. 2006)]
Epithelial ovarian cancer	β -HCH, endosulfan I, p,p'-DDT, p,p'-DDE,heptachlor	[(Sharma et al. 2015)]
Uterine cervix cancer	Aldrin, DDE. g-HCH, endosulfan, heptachlor	[(Polanco Rodríguez et al. 2017)]
Bladder Cancer	p,p'-DDD, p,p'-DDT, p,p'-DDE	(Boada et al. 2016)
Malignant breast cancer	p,p0-DDT, PCBs	[(Wassermann et al. 1976)]
Invasive ductal cancer (IDC)	HCH, PCTA and pp-DDE	[(Yang et al. 2015)]
Induce breast cancer cell proliferation	p,p0-DDE	[(Aubé et al. 2011)]
K-ras mutations in pancreatic cancer	p,p0-DDT	[(López et al. 2014)]
colorectal cancer growth	p,p'- DDT	(Song et al., 2014)

pancreatic cancer	DDE, DDT and PCBs	(Hoppin et al. 2000)
Metastatic Prostate Cancer	[β -HCH, γ -HCH, DDT, DDE	(Koutros et al. 2015)
Depression	Aldrin,	[(Beard et al. 2013)]
Cardiovascular disease	PCB	(Kim et al. 2015)
Alzheimer's disease (AD)	Aroclor	[(Medehouenou et al., 2014)]
Autism spectrum disorders (ASD)	p,p'-DDE	[(Ornoy et al. 2015)]
Parkinson's disease (PD)	DDT	[(Roberts et al. 2007)]
	Endosulfan	[(Caudle et al. 2005; Wilson et al. 2014)
	Heptachlor	(Chen et al. 2017)]
decreased sperm concentration	Higher p,p-DDE concentrations	(Aneck-Hahn et al. 2007)
a decreased sperm concentration	DT-DDE	(Messaroset al., 2009)

chronic bronchitis	DDT exposures	(Hoppin et al. 2008; Kolani et al. 2016)
asthma		
metabolic syndrome (hypertension, central obesity, dyslipidemia and dysglycemia)	PCBs.	(Rosenbaum et al. 2017)
Insulin resistance and diabetes	PCBs	(Lee et al. 2011)
Decrease sperm quality	DDT, HCH	(Perry 2008)

Toxicity mechanism of organochlorine insecticides.

The CYP450 family of enzymes is important for both the activation and detoxification of OPs. The relative rates at which organophosphorothioates (OPTs) insecticides are activated and detoxified maybe an important determinant of toxicity. Independently of the chemical structure, bioactivation of OPTs such as malathion, chlorpyrifos, diazinon, azynphos-methyl and parathion to the very highly toxic oxon forms are carried out by the same CYP450 systems (Buratti et al. 2005). These insecticides feature a thiophosphate moiety that is subjected to oxidative desulfuration in which the CYP450s remove the sulfur atom attached to the phosphorus and insert atomic oxygen (**Fig. 2**). This results in covalent binding of sulfur to CYP, a reaction that occurs preferentially at cysteine residues leading to an irreversible inactivation of the enzymes that catalyzes the reactions. This mechanism-based inhibition of CYP450 is a suicide reaction for the P450 carrying out the reaction (Hodgson and Rose, 2007; Kyle et al., 2013).

Fig. 2. Specific CYP450s may both bio activate the parent organophosphorothioates (OPTs) to highly toxic oxon forms and concurrently detoxify them by dearylation to form dialkylthiophosphates (DATPs), inactive metabolites. CYP2C9 or CYP2C19 are the isoforms responsible for the dearylation reaction. Bio activation of OPTs is also carried out by CYP450 systems. At low concentrations, oxon derivatives formation is catalyzed by CYP1A2 and CYP2B6, whereas CYP3A4 is relevant only at high concentrations. The oxon form is a strong esterase inhibitor that can be effectively scavenged by pseudo cholinesterase (BChE) and carboxylesterases (CEs), and the remaining free (non-detoxified) amount may reach target organs where inhibit acetylcholinesterase. The oxon can be alternatively hydrolyzed by paraoxonase-1 (PON1) yielding dialkylphosphates (DAPs), inactive metabolites that are excreted through the urine. OPT insecticides feature a thio-phosphate moiety that is subjected to oxidative desulfuration in which the CYP450s remove the sulfur atom attached to the phosphorus and insert atomic oxygen. This is a suicide reaction for the P450 carrying out the reaction. Given that organochlorine pesticides, such as endosulfan- and DDT, are CYP3A4 inducers, prior exposure to these compounds can potentiate OPs toxicity, particularly when these compounds occur at high concentrations. (Hernández et al. 2013) with slight modification

Organochlorine pesticides residues in Environment

As pesticides are designed to be toxic to particular groups of organisms, they can have considerable adverse environmental effects on other living creatures as well as diverse media including air, soil, or water (Aktar et al., 2009). Organochlorine pesticide pollution in various environmental media (such as air, water, and soil) as given below.

Organochlorine pesticide residues in air

Pesticides from non-target crops or volatilization from the treated area may contaminate air, soil, and water. Various instances of pesticide drift occur during every application, even from ground equipment (Yates et al., 2002). Pesticide drift accounts for approximately 2 to 25% chemical loss during application; this can spread over a wide area, from a few yards to several hundred miles. There are many cases of pesticides drifting, in the world, every year (Que et al., 1975). More than 80–90% of pesticides are volatilized within a few days of application on crops or in the health sector (Majewski and Capel, 1995). Atmospheric sources of OCPs include direct emissions and Volatilizes from the surface of water and soil. Many pesticides volatilize (i.e. evaporate from the soil and foliage, and move away from the initial application area) and reach into every area of the environment, thereby contaminating them adversely (U.S. Geological Surve, 1995; Rodríguez et al., 2018). Higher levels of HCHs and DDTs were reported in the tropical coastal atmosphere from India and were measured in higher amounts tween 1.45–35.6 ng m⁻³ and 0.16–5.93 ng m⁻³, respectively (Babu et al., 2003) Highly populated and agricultural areas along Indian coastal length and industrial and agricultural areas of Punjab Province, Pakistan were also found contaminated with higher levels of OCPs (Zhang et al. 2008; Syed et al., 2013).

Organochlorine pesticide residues in soil

Sediment is an environmental matrix which is considered as the ultimate sink for POPs (Bhattacharya et al., 2003) and is considered as the best media for temporary and long term monitoring of contaminants (Guzzella et al., 2005). Sediments are mainly comprised of organic, inorganic particles and detritus which are relatively heterogeneous in terms of biological, physical and chemical characteristics (Bhattacharya et al., 2003). POPs make their way to sediments through surface runoff, leaching, vapour phase, ultimately accumulation and settling in sediments (Sarkar et al., 2008) for a very long time due to their long half- lifetimes (El Nemr et al., 2013). Glaciers are one of the major sources of POPs as they transport huge amounts of rock debris and sediments in their load (Encyclopedia of Earth, 2015). During the water runoff from glaciers, higher amounts of sediments move in the plains and rivers. These

sediments contain some POPs in higher concentrations as compared to the water samples based on hydrophobic properties of POPs i.e., the levels of HCH concentrations were fairly low in water samples when compared to the sediments (Sarkar et al., 2008). The authors highlighted weathered and aged agricultural soils were the main sources of contamination of DDT in the sediments. Furthermore, another important source was suggested to be the recent illegal use of DDT in the river catchments even after its ban in the country (Malik et al., 2009). (Bhattacharya et al., 2003) reported increasing levels of HCHs, DDTs and endosulfan sulfate during pre-monsoon months. The order of OCPs was in the following pattern: HCHs > endosulfan sulfate > DDTs > α -endosulfan. Among the DDT metabolites, p-p' -DDT and p' -p' -DDE were found at higher levels with almost 70 to 90% of the total DDTs in the sediments. This distribution of metabolites indicated that DDT was actively degraded in the sediments via dehydrochlorination produced either by biotic or by the abiotic decomposition reaction. Domestic and industrial discharges, extensive agricultural chemicals application and soil erosion were considered as the main sources of OCPs in the study area. At the same location again, (Malik et al. 2009) conducted another study to analyze DDT in soil depths and results revealed that up to 91% of soil samples were found contaminated with DDT along with 67% of those samples that showed the residual DDT levels higher than the value of DDT minimum risk level in the soils ($0.05 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). (Yadav et al., 1981) also reported upward and increasing trend of DDT near the surrounding area of DDT manufacturing plant. According to the authors, the mean value of DDT was 0.34 ppm in 1974, which became upward in 1978 to 1.43 ppm and in 1983 to 1.67 ppm. The authors also suggested the decrease in levels of residual DDT as the distance from the DDT manufacturing plant increases.

Persistent organochlorine pesticide residues in water.

OCPs can enter into the aquatic environment through several routes and processes. Major sources and routes into the water included deposition and air-water exchange processes (Guzzella et al., 2011), used as pesticides for crops and malarial control (Ahad et al., 2010; 2001; Ali M, 1991; Tariq et al., 2006), ponding irrigation, leaching (Flury et al. 1994), careless disposal of pesticide containers, agricultural runoff and washing of equipment's (Ahad et al., 2010; 2001; Tariq et al., 2006, 2004). In Pakistan, it has been reported that groundwater contamination with persistent chemicals is greatly attributed to many factors including shallow water, characteristics of soil and rigorous spraying of the pesticides (Jabbar et al., 1993; Tariq et al., 2004a; 2007b) Among all the components of DDT and HCH, p,p-DDT & γ -HCH were present in major amount in the contaminated water samples collected from India. The

contribution of o,p-DDT, p,p-DDT, p,p-DDE, α -HCH, β -HCH, γ -HCH, heptachlor epoxide & Dieldrin were 66.67 % (2008), 66.67 % (2009) and 33.33 %.

Persistent organochlorine pesticide residues in food.

Some classes of pesticides manifest their harm to human health both as exterior discomfort and internal, less visible damage to the body. Pesticide residues are present in all agroecosystems, but the real risk to human health is through exposure to residues in primary and derived agricultural products (Jeyaratnam, 1990). Though the application of OCPs has been prohibited in many of the countries, they are still marketed and present in the environment and human body tissues (Needham et al., 2005; Freire et al., 2014). The persistence of OCPs in the food chain and the environment are linked to their slow breakdown and lipophilicity, disposal from animal bodies is a slow process. These pesticides are deposited in the individual adipose cells by making use of infected food, particularly fish and animal fat, consequently the building-up and causing harm to the organism (Davis et al., 1993; Barnhoorn et al., 2009). Persistence pollutant in the food chain may also be responsible for acute effects like simple skin and eyes discomfort the general malaise and to serious, chronic problems related to the neurological system as well as light intellectual malfunction (e.g. neurobehavioral modifications feelings changes,), psychomotor malfunction, depressive mood and loss of life due to mental illness, neurodegenerative diseases (e.g. Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases) and serious neurodevelopment problems and cancers (Migliore and Coppedè, 2009; Kanthasamy et al., 2012; Mustafa et al., 2013). In Nigeria, organochlorines are most common pesticides applied to food crops on the field and during storage (State, 2011). The pesticides detected in the cereal grains in present study were in the following range; Aldrin (0.03 to 0.13 mg/kg), Dichloran (0.01 mg/kg), Dieldrin (0.018 to 0.02 mg/kg), Endrin (0.0003 to 0.03 mg/kg), Endosulfan (0.005 to 0.02 mg/kg), Heptachlor epoxide (0.02 mg/kg), Lindane (0.25 to 1.25 mg/kg), Methoxychlor (0.03 to 1.17), Mirex (0.008 to 0.02 mg/kg), DDT (0.04 mg/kg) respectively (Anzene et al. 2014). Beef samples from Buoho had DDE concentration of 31.89 μ g/kg in the fat and 5.86 μ g/kg in the lean beef. 1, 1, 1-trichloro-2, 2-bis-(4'-chlorophenyl) ethane (DDT) recorded an average concentration of 545.22 μ g/kg in beef fat and 18.85 μ g/kg in lean beef samples from Kumasi abattoir (Darko and Acquah, 2007). The concentration level of the studied organochlorines followed the order: p, p' dichloro-diphenyl-trichloroethane (DDT) > endosulfan > p'-DDT > lindane > dieldrin > endrin > aldrin > chlorothanolin while the order of contamination in the analyzed organs was liver > kidney > meat. Heat treatment of the meat, kidney and liver samples (boiling for 90 min.) produced an overall reduction of 62.2%, 44.5%, 37.7%, 29%, 31%, 34.3% and 30.8% in lindane, o, p'-DDT, endosulfan, p, p'-DDT,

chlorothalonil, aldrin, dieldrin, and endrin, respectively (Letta and Attah 2013). One of the methods used to reduce the effect of pesticide residue in food is to eat organic foods than non-organic ones. According to standard meta-analyses the frequency of occurrence of detectable pesticide residues was four times higher in non-organic crops than organic crops (Baranski et al 2014) there is evidence that indicated organic food consumption can reduce exposure to pesticide residues in food (Smith-Spangler et al., 2012).

Human exposure to organochlorine pesticides

Human exposure to insecticides begins during the period of early prenatal stage and lasts through to the (breast-feeding) neonatal periods, and these stages are very critical for the normal development and differentiation of various sensitive body organs and systems. In fact after exposure, these toxic chemicals cross the placenta to the foetus and are secreted into the breast milk (Perera et al., 2005). The dietary exposure route in adults accounts for more than 90% of total exposure, while workers may also be exposed through inhalation and skin contact of the organochlorine compound. Organochlorine compounds are rapidly absorbed by the small intestine and enter into the circulatory system where they distributed throughout the different body parts and stored in body tissues with high lipid contents. As a result of the constant exchange between blood and tissues, these toxic chemicals can pass into the bloodstream (cord blood, whole blood, serum and plasma tissues), adipose tissue (in autopsies and living subjects), muscles, and hair and breast milk (Tsatsakis and Tutudaki, 2008; Adu-Kumi et al., 2010; Covaci et al., 2002; Dewailly et al., 1999; Jakszyn et al., 2009; Kawakami et al., 2017; Król et al., 2013; Li et al., 2008). Exposure to persistent organochlorine chemicals are found to be associated with health effects including cancer (Aronson et al., 2000; Arrebola et al., 2015; Cohn et al., 2015; Mathur et al., 2002), reproductive defects (Nicolopoulou-Stamati and Pitsos 2001) and behavioural changes (Zala and Penn, 2004). Further studies show that these effects are believed to be associated to their capability to disrupt the function of specific enzymes, hormones, growth factors, neurotransmitters as well as to inducing key genes involved with the metabolism of steroids and xenobiotic (Kleanthi et al., 2008).

Pesticides are formulated to control or eliminate harmful unwanted pests, but it is not surprising that a formulation designed to interfere with an animal's biological functioning can also lead human health and fitness issues through the stimulation of diverse human physiological processes. Previous work shows that pesticide sprays can indeed be harmful to workers, consumers and any person involved in their handling, production and transport (Luminita, 2017; Saeedi and Shokrzadeh, 2014; Shokrzadeh and Saeedi, 2009). Moreover, there is evidence risk of contracting cancer may be raised not just for those handling pesticides, but

also for the general population living in an area with higher exposure of pesticides in the environment (Parro'n et al., 2014).

Some classes of pesticides manifest their harm to human health as both exterior discomfort and internal, less visible damage to the body. Though the application of OCPs has been prohibited in many of the countries, they are still marketed and present in the environment and human body tissues (Needham et al., 2005; Freire et al. 2014). The persistence of OCPs in the food chain and the environment is linked to their slow breakdown and lipophilicity, disposal from animal bodies is a slow process. These pesticides are deposited in the individual adipose cells by making use of infected food, particularly fish and animal fat, consequently the building-up and causing harm to the organism (Davis et al., 1993; Barnhoorn et al., 2009). The side effects due to the exposure to OCPs is dependent on the type used and mode of inducing pest mortality, level of exposure and length of exposure is also critical. Exposure in the environment then allows the pesticides to enter the body through the four major tracks, such as breathing, skin, dental, and ocular (Shokrzadeh and Saravi, 2009). Exposure in the environment then allows the pesticides to enter the body through the four major tracks, such as breathing, skin, dental, and ocular (Saeedi and Shokrzadeh, 2014)

Adverse effects of organochlorine pesticides exposure on human health

Organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) such as dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), hexachlorocyclohexanes (HCHs), chlordane, hexa-chlorobenzene (HCB) and Mirex are persistent, lipophilic chemicals that are known to accumulate in human tissues (Lange et al., 2014). They also degrade slowly in humans, animals, air, water and soil and are subject to long-range transport (Yu et al., 2013; Sharma et al., 2014). Thus, exposure to OCPs has been associated with human health risk of arthritis, skin disease, bone disorder, endocrine disruption, developmental abnormalities, reproduction failure, and cancer and nerve disorder. For humans, food is the major pathway for exposure to OCPs (Sudaryanto et al., 2006; Hedley et al., 2010) The risk of health hazards due to organochlorine pesticides exposure depends not only on how toxic the ingredients are but also on the level of exposure. In addition, certain people such as children, pregnant women, or aging populations may be more sensitive to the effects of pesticides than other chemicals.

Cancers

Pesticides constitute a diverse class of chemicals extensively used for prevention of harmful effects caused by pests. Among the large number of different pesticides those that are of particular concern is organochlorines (OCs), exposure to an environmental

comprised of widely used chemicals designed to treat pests (e.g., insects), have been associated with adverse human health outcomes such as cancers (Alavanja et al., 2004; Blair et al., 2015). reproductive defects (Nicolopoulou-Stamati and Pitsos 2001) and behavioural changes (Zala and Penn, 2004). Numerous experiments have confirmed the harmful effects of DDT on humans (Cárdenas-González et al., 2013; Wong et al., 2015). **(Table 2)**. There are four broad categories of risk factors for cancer including lifestyle, genetic/familial, reproductive/hormonal and environmental. However, these known risk aspects describe only a small fraction of cases. Further studies show that the hormones effects and environmental factors are becoming increasingly important as breast cancer risk factors (Fredslund and Jørgensen, 2012; Olsen et al., 1997; Salehi et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2015). Research focusing on agricultural workers, indicate that a greater risk of prostate cancer may be associated with the use of pesticides, primary amongst them being OCPs (Band et al., 2011) Moreover, some of the OCPs, e.g. DDT, HCH, chlordane, HCB, and heptachlor, have been found to be ‘most likely carcinogenic’ to human (Group 2B) by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (Stewart and Wild, 2014). Organochlorine pesticides were reported to increase the risk of hormone-related cancers including breast, prostate, stomach and lung cancer (Wolf et al., 1993). Recently dioxins have been found in human ovarian follicular fluid, which may lead to the development of endometriosis. Exposure to dioxins can cause several autoimmune diseases, including multiple sclerosis and eczema (Sinaii et al., 2002). Organochlorines can function as xenoestrogens and compounds such as TCDD, methoxychlor and alachlor were reported to exert effects on human and experimental animals due to inhibited synthesis and increased degradation of thyroid hormones. Moreover, it has been reported that the negative effects of organochlorine pesticide may not be universally applicable and may be dependent on their particular distribution and use. Securing the environmental safety, reliability of the quality of pesticides and safety in its application are widely seen as important challenges for pesticide governance, As a result, small-hold farmers have suffered problems due to the lack of proper information available regarding the safety and correct use of pesticides (Belay et al., 2015).

Table. 2 some important organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), their chemical structures, toxicity, Chemical type and persistence in environment. Copy from (Jayaraj et al., 2016) with slight modification.

Chemical name	Structural formula	Chemical Type	Toxicity LD ₅₀	WHO classification based on rat oral LD ₅₀	Persistence in environment
(1) Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) C ₁₄ H ₉ Cl ₅		Acaricide Insecticide	<p>Rat:</p> <p>Oral: 113–130 mg/kg</p> <p>Dermal: 2510 mg/kg</p> <p>Mice</p> <p>Oral: 150–300 mg/kg</p> <p>Gunia Pigs</p> <p>Oral: 300 mg/kg</p> <p>Rabbit</p> <p>Oral: 400 mg/kg</p>	Moderately hazardous	High Persistence Half-life: 2–15 years

<p>(2)</p> <p>1,1-dichloro-2,2bis (p-chlorophenyl)ethane (DDD)</p>	<p>Insecticide</p>	<p>Rat: Oral: 4000 mg/kg</p>	<p>Acute hazard is unlikely</p>	<p>High Persistence Half-life: 5–10 years</p>
<p>(3)</p> <p>Dichloro diphenyl dichloroethane (DDE)</p>	<p>Insecticide</p>	<p>Rat: Oral: 800–1240 mg/kg</p>	<p>Slightly hazardous</p>	<p>High Persistence Half-life: 10 years</p>
<p>(4)</p> <p>Dicofol C₁₄H₉Cl₅O</p>	<p>Acaricide</p>	<p>Rat: Oral: 684–1495 mg/kg</p> <p>Rabbit: Oral: 1810 mg/kg Dermal: 2.1 g/kg</p>	<p>Moderately hazardous</p>	<p>Moderate persistence Half-life: 60 days</p>

(5)		Avicide insecticide	Rat: Oral: 3 mg/kg Dermal: 15 mg/kg	Highly hazardous	Moderate Persistence Half-life: 1Day to 12 Years
			Mouse: Oral: 1.37g/kg Intravenous: 2300 g/kg		

(6)		Insecticide	Rat: Oral: 46 mg/kg Dermal: 50–120 mg/kg	Highly hazardous	High Persistence Half-life: 9 months
			Mouse: Oral: 38–77 mg/kg Dog: Oral: 56–120 mg/kg Rabbit: Oral: 45–50 mg/kg		

(7)

Chlordane

C₁₀H₆Cl₈

Insecticide

Rat:

Oral: 200 to 700 mg/kg

Dermal: 530–690 mg/

kg

Mice:

Oral: 145–430 mg/kg

Dermal: 153 mg/kg

Rabbit:

Dermal: 780 mg/kg

Moderately
hazardous

High
Persistence

Half-life: 10
years

(8)

Heptachlor

C₁₀H₅Cl₇

Insecticide

Rat:

Oral: 40– 220 mg/kg

Dermal: 119–320 mg/kg

Mouse:

Oral: 30–68 mg/kg

Rabbit:

Highly –
Moderately
hazardous

High
Persistence

Half-life: 2
years

Dermal: 2000 mg/kg

(9)

Endosulfan

C₉H₆Cl₆O₃S

Insecticide

Rat:

Oral: 18 to 220 mg/kg

Dermal: 74 mg/kg

Rabbits:

Dermal: 200–359 mg/kg

Highly hazardous

Moderate
Persistence

Half life

Alpha
Isomer: 35 days
Beta
Isomer: 150 days

(10)

Lindane

C₆H₆Cl₆

Acaricide

Insecticide

Rodenticide

Rat:

Oral: 88 – 270 mg/kg

Mouse:

Oral: 59–246 mg/kg

Moderately
hazardous

High
Persistence

Half-life:

15 months

(11)

Aldrin

C₁₂H₈Cl₆

Insecticide

Oral: 39 to 60 mg/kg

Dermal: 100 mg/kg

Mouse:

Oral: 44 mg/kg

Dog:

Oral: 65–95 mg/kg

Highly hazardous

Moderate
Persistence

Half-life:

4–7 years

Respiratory and skin diseases

According to the World Health Organization, chronic respiratory diseases, including asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), were the leading cause of total world morbidity (6.2%) and the third leading cause of all global deaths (7.1%) in 2008 (Physician, 2014). Asthma is the most common chronic disease, affecting ~14% of children in the world, and its prevalence has been increasing for several decades (Pearce et al., 2007). In addition, respiratory diseases are the most common causes of death among children under 5 years of age (Phuong et al., 2017). It is now accepted that, besides viruses and bacteria, environmental agents can induce or exacerbate airway inflammation, which can be a predictor of chronic respiratory diseases (Dalphin JC, 1998; Michielsen et al., 2002). **(Table 2)**. Some environmental risk factors are now well known, such as allergens, tobacco smoke, gaseous or particulate air pollutants, and exposure to certain chemicals, such as pesticides (Bessot et al., 1996; Hoppin et al., 2003). However, the overuse of these agro-chemical substances may have effects on community health, mainly in vulnerable populations, for example, children and pregnant women living in agriculture areas. It has been demonstrated through biomonitoring, that in agricultural areas inhabitants have elevated urinary levels of pesticide metabolites. Persistence pollutant in the food chain may also be responsible for acute effects like simple skin and eyes discomfort to the general malaise and serious, chronic problems related to the neurological system as well as light intellectual malfunction (e.g. neurobehavioral modifications feelings changes,), psychomotor malfunction, depressive mood and loss of life due to mental illness, neurodegenerative diseases (e.g. Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases) and serious neurodevelopment problems and cancers (Migliore and Coppedè, 2009; Kanthasamy et al., 2012; Mustafa et al., 2013). Moreover, some of the OCPs, e.g. DDT, HCH, chlordane, HCB, and heptachlor, have been found to be 'most likely carcinogenic' to human (Group 2B) by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (Stewart and Wild, 2014). Pesticide classification is currently set according to WHO categories, which is based on the threat posed by the use of the pesticide, and these have been divided in the following categories **Table 3**.

Table 3. Classification of pesticides. Based on toxicity criteria (World Health Organization, 2010)

Type	Toxicity level	LD ₅₀ for the rate (mg/Kg body weight)	
		Oral	Dermal
la	Extremely hazardous	<5	<5
lb	Highly hazardous	5-50	5-50
II	Moderately hazardous	50-2000	50-2000
U	Unlikely to present acute hazard	2000 or higher	-----

Other related diseases caused by the exposure of OCP

Some classes of pesticides manifest their harm to human health as both exterior discomfort and internal, less visible damage to the body. Though the application of OCPs has been prohibited in many of the countries, they are still marketed and present in the environment and human body tissues (Needham et al., 2005; Freire et al., 2014). In children, exposure to dioxins showed significant positive associations with a learning disability (LD) (Lee et al., 2007). Risk of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) at higher levels of p,p'-DDE and PCBs exposure was reported (Sagiv et al., 2010). Prenatal exposure to p,p'-DDE and its presence in cord serum was found to lead to the disappearance of neuronal development after 12 months of infant age (Torres-Sánchez et al., 2009). Epidemiological studies have shown that exposure to persistent organic pollutants, mainly organochlorine pesticides, is strongly associated with type 2 diabetes. Some persistent organic pollutants, as highly chlorinated PCBs and trans nonachlor, were associated with the incidence of type 2 diabetes in obese people (Lee et al., 2006). Detection of organochlorine pesticides from human breast milk was reported from many places in the world. In Croatia, p,p'-DDE was found to be the dominant organochlorine pesticide in human breast milk (Klinčić et al., 2014). Exposure of infants to chlordane via breast milk was reported as a potential health risk in Korea (Lee et al., 2013). Another study from Korea also revealed the presence of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) chlordane, aldrin, dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDTs), dieldrin, heptachlor, endrin, hexachlorocyclohexanes (HCHs), hexachlorobenzene (HCB), toxaphene and mirex, in the milk (Kim et al., 2013). Organochlorine pesticides HCB, β -HCH, pp'DDE, pp'DDT, pp'DDT, Σ -DDT were present in breast milk of the population in Guerrero, Mexico, proportionally to exposure (Chávez-Almazán et al., 2014). Several of the most prevalent forms include leukaemia, non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, and brain, bone, breast, ovarian, prostate, testicular and liver cancers (Cantor et al., 1992). A study reported that children who live in homes where their parents use pesticides are twice as likely to develop brain cancer as those that live in residences in which no pesticides are used (Bradman et al., 2007; CDC, 2011). There is also mounting evidence that exposure to organochlorine pesticides disrupts the endocrine system (Mnif et al., 2011), the reproductive system, and embryonic development. Endocrine disruption can cause infertility and a variety of birth defects and developmental defects in offspring, including hormonal imbalances and incomplete sexual development, impaired brain development, behavioural disorders, and many others (Alavanja et al., 2004).

Prospects and conclusions.

Although pesticides are developed to prevent or control insect pests in the agricultural system. The current review reveals that higher levels of OCPs are widely distributed in different environmental compartments and food, which causes serious harmful effects on human health. There are indeed many inherent problems in conducting large-scale trials to directly assess the causality of human health issues related to the use of pesticides. The excess consumption of pesticides contributes in the accumulation of pesticide residues in food grains and vegetables associated with a variety of human health hazards, including damage to central and peripheral nervous systems, cancer, allergies and hypersensitivities, reproductive disorders, and disruption of the immune system. The impact of pesticide residues can be minimized by preventive measures such as rational use of pesticides, washing and proper processing of food products, practicing organic farming, use of natural pesticides, bio-pesticides, and strict implementation and amendment of pesticide-related laws.

To reduce the risk posed by exposure to OCPs we need to drastically reduce the presence of harmful chemicals in our ecosphere (our air, water, ground and food). There should be a further application of non-toxic and cultural methods of agriculture to achieve sustainable control of our insect and weed problems rather than maintaining a reliance on pesticide synthetic compounds. Plant-derived chemical components and sustainable methods of biological control are key to our community's health and health of the ecosphere. Stricter regulations regarding aerial spraying and establishment of buffer areas could be implemented to reduce the effects of drift. A reduction in the application of OCPs to crops, soil and water systems may be achieved through using non-chemical control methods to way to kill pests use. The public should be informed of the threat of diseases caused by the exposure of OCPs and the link to exposure to those facing frequent exposure should be carefully monitored for the development of diseases. Laboratory testing should be available for assessing OCPs like DDE and, PCBs and the major metabolite of DDT, in blood vessels or adipose cells. The sharing of data acquired through monitoring should be anonymised and be made available as widely as possible to allow interpretation by the wider scientific community. Women should be made aware of the potential risks associated with breast-feeding if they have been subjected to OCPs. Otherwise, the overall health benefits of breast-feeding may be outweighed by any threat of exposure of the baby to OCPs. Lastly, ongoing study is needed on these pollutants, their body burden, prospective health effects and methods to diminish their bioavailability in food and environment. Additionally, effective strategies are needed to control their manufacturing and release into the atmosphere.

References.

- A.M.TsatsakisM.N.TzatzarakisM.Tutudaki (2008) Pesticide levels in head hair samples of Cretan population as an indicator of present and past exposure. *Forensic Sci Int* 176:67–71
- A NR, Frances Gulland a B, C GMY, et al Sentinel California sea lions provide insight into legacy organochlorine exposure trends and their association with cancer and infectious disease. *One Heal* 1:37–43
- Abhilash PC, Singh N (2009) Pesticide use and application: An Indian scenario. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 165:1–12
- Adu-Kumi S, Kawano M, Shiki Y (2010) Organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls (dl-PCBs), polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins and polychlorinated dibenzo furans (PCDD/Fs) in edible fish from Lake Volta, Lake Bosumtwi and Weiija Lake in Ghana. *Chemosphere* 81:675–684. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2010.08.018
- Afful S, Anim AK (2010) Spectrum of Organochlorine Pesticide Residues in Fish Samples from the Densu Basin. *Res J Environ Earth Sci* 2:133–138
- Ahad K, Hayat Y, Ahmad I SM (2001) Capillary chromatographic determination of pesti- cides residues in groundwater of Multan Division. *Nucleus* 38:145–9
- Ahad K, Mohammad A, Khan H (2010) Monitoring results for organochlorine pesticides in soil and water from selected obsolete pesticide stores in Pakistan. *Environ Monit Assess* 166:191–199. doi: 10.1007/s10661-009-0995-5
- Aiyesanmi, A.F., Idowu1 G. (2012) Organochlorine pesticides residues in soil of cocoa farms in Ondo State Central District, Nigeria. *Environ Nat Resour Res* 2:65–73
- Aktar W, Sengupta D, Chowdhury A (2009) Impact of pesticides use in agriculture: Their benefits and hazards. *Interdiscip Toxicol* 2:1–12. doi: 10.2478/v10102-009-0001-7
- Alavanja MCR, Hoppin JA, Kamel F (2004) Health Effects of Chronic Pesticide Exposure: Cancer and Neurotoxicity. *Annu Rev Public Health* 25:155–197. doi: 10.1146/annurev.publhealth.25.101802.123020
- Alcock, R.; Bashkin, V.; Bisson, M.; Brecher, R.; van Bree, L.; Chrast R (2008) Joint WHO/convention task force on the health aspects of air pollution. Health risks of persistent organic pollutants from long-range transboundary air pollution. World Heal Organ Copenhagen Regional Office for Europe: 2003 Available from:/h
- Ali M JA (1991) Effect of pesticides and fertilizers on shallow groundwater quality. Pakistan Council for Research in Water Resources. Final Tech Report;
- Ali U, Syed JH, Malik RN (2014) Organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) in South Asian region: A review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 476–477:705–717
- Amdur MO, Doull J, Klaassen CD (1992) Casarett and Doull’s Toxicology: The Basic Science of Poisons. *J Occup Environ Med* 35:76. doi: 10.1136/pgmj.63.746.1112-b
- Androutopoulos VP, Hernandez AF, Liesivuori J, Tsatsakis AM (2013) A mechanistic overview of health associated effects of low levels of organochlorine and organophosphorous pesticides. *Toxicology* 307:89–94. doi: 10.1016/j.tox.2012.09.011
- Aneck-Hahn NH, Schulenburg GW, Bornman MS (2007) Impaired semen quality associated with

- environmental DDT exposure in young men living in a malaria area in the Limpopo Province, South Africa. *J Androl* 28:423–434. doi: 10.2164/jandrol.106.001701
- Anzene JS, Tyohemba RL, Ahile UJ, Emezi KSA (2014) Organochlorine pesticide residues analysis of postharvest cereal grains in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Int J Agron Agric Res* 5:2223–7054
- Appenzeller BMR, Tsatsakis AM (2012) Hair analysis for biomonitoring of environmental and occupational exposure to organic pollutants: State of the art, critical review and future needs. *Toxicol. Lett.* 210:119–140
- Aronson KJ, Miller AB, Woolcott CG (2000) Breast adipose tissue concentrations of polychlorinated biphenyls and other organochlorines and breast cancer risk. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev* 9:55–63
- Arrebola JP, Belhassen H, Artacho-Cordón F (2015a) Risk of female breast cancer and serum concentrations of organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls: A case-control study in Tunisia. *Sci Total Environ* 520:106–113. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.03.045
- Arrebola JP, Belhassen H, Artacho-Cordón F (2015b) Risk of female breast cancer and serum concentrations of organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls: a case-control study in Tunisia. *Sci Total Environ* 520:106–113. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.03.045
- Aubé M, Larochelle C, Ayotte P (2011) Differential effects of a complex organochlorine mixture on the proliferation of breast cancer cell lines. *Environ Res* 111:337–347. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2011.01.010
- Augustijn-Beckers PW, Hornsby AG WR (1994) Additional Properties Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology,. CS/ARS/CES Pestic Prop Database Environ Decis II 137
- Babu GS, Farooq M, Ray RS (2003) DDT and HCH residues in Basmati rice (*Oryza sativa*) cultivated in Dehradun (India). *Water Air Soil Pollut* 144:149–157. doi: 10.1023/A:1022929502510
- Band PR, Abanto Z, Bert J (2011) Prostate cancer risk and exposure to pesticides in British Columbia Farmers. *Prostate* 71:168–183. doi: 10.1002/pros.21232
- Baranski, M., Srednicka-Tober, D., Volakakis, N. (2014) Higher antioxidant and lower cadmium concentrations and lower incidence of pesticide residues in organically grown crops. a Syst Lit Rev meta-analyses 12:794–811
- Barnhoorn IEJ, Bornman MS, Jansen van Rensburg C, Bouwman H (2009) DDT residues in water, sediment, domestic and indigenous biota from a currently DDT-sprayed area. *Chemosphere* 77:1236–1241. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2009.08.045
- Beard JD, Hoppin JA, Richards M, et al (2013) Pesticide exposure and self-reported incident depression among wives in the Agricultural Health Study. *Environ Res* 126:31–42. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2013.06.001
- Belay T, Woldegiorgis H, Gress T, Rayyan Y (2015) Intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy with concomitant hepatitis C virus infection, Joan C. Edwards SOM, Marshall University. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol* 27:372–374. doi: 10.1097/MEG.0000000000000293
- Belta, G.D., Likata, P., Bruzzese, A., Naccarri, C., Trombetta, D., Turco, V.L., Dugo, C. R, A., Naccari F (2006) Level and congener pattern of PCBs and OCPs residues in blue-fin tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*) from the straits of Messina. *Environ Int* 32:705–710
- Bessot JC, Blaumeiser M KM (1996) asthme professionnel en milieu agricole [Occupational asthma in an agricultural setting. *Rev Mal Respir* 13:205–215

- Bhattacharya B, Sarkar SK, Mukherjee N (2003) Organochlorine pesticide residues in sediments of a tropical mangrove estuary, India: Implications for monitoring. *Environ Int* 29:587–592. doi: 10.1016/S0160-4120(03)00016-3
- Blair A, Ritz B, Wesseling C, Beane Freeman L (2015) Pesticides and human health. *Occup Env Med* 72:81–82. doi: 10.1136/oemed-2014-102454
- Boada LD, Henríquez-Hernández LA, Zumbado M (2016) Organochlorine Pesticides Exposure and Bladder Cancer: Evaluation from a Gene-Environment Perspective in a Hospital-Based Case-Control Study in the Canary Islands (Spain). *J Agromedicine* 21:34–42. doi: 10.1080/1059924X.2015.1106374
- Bradman A, Whitaker D, Quirós L (2007) Pesticides and their metabolites in the homes and urine of farmworker children living in the Salinas Valley, CA. In: *Journal of Exposure Science and Environmental Epidemiology*. pp 331–349
- Buratti FM, D’Aniello A, Volpe M, et al (2005) Malathion bioactivation in the human liver: The contribution of different cytochrome P450 isoforms. *Drug Metab Dispos* 33:295–302. doi: 10.1124/dmd.104.001693
- Cantor KP, Blair A, Everett G (1992) Pesticides and Other Agricultural Risk-Factors for Non-Hodgkins-Lymphoma Among Men in Iowa and Minnesota. *Cancer Res* 52:2447–2455
- Cárdenas-González MC, Del Razo LM, Barrera-Chimal j (2013) Proximal renal tubular injury in rats sub-chronically exposed to low fluoride concentrations. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 272:888–894. doi: 10.1016/j.taap.2013.07.026
- Caudle WM, Richardson JR, Wang M, Miller GW (2005) Perinatal heptachlor exposure increases expression of presynaptic dopaminergic markers in mouse striatum. In: *NeuroToxicology*. pp 721–728
- CDC (Centers for Disease Control P (2011) Pesticide exposure in children living in agricultural areas along the United States–Mexico Border, Yuma County, Arizona. Office of Border Health, Arizona Department of Health Services; 2002. Arizona Dep Heal Serv Available: http://www.epa.gov/icc/projects_publica
- Centers for disease control and prevention (CDC) (2017) Fourth National Report on Human Exposure to Environmental Chemicals. Fourth Natl Rep Hum Expo to Environ Chem Updat Tables, January 2017
- Chávez-Almazán LA, Díaz-Ortiz JS, Alarcón-Romero M (2014) Organochlorine pesticide levels in breast milk in guerrero, Mexico. *Bull Environ Contam Toxicol* 93:. doi: 10.1007/s00128-014-1308-4
- Chen T, Tan J, Wan Z, et al (2017) Effects of commonly used pesticides in China on the mitochondria and ubiquitin-proteasome system in Parkinson’s disease. *Int J Mol Sci* 18:. doi: 10.3390/ijms18122507
- Cohn BA, La Merrill M, Krigbaum NY (2015) DDT exposure in utero and breast cancer. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 100:2865–2872. doi: 10.1210/jc.2015-1841
- Covaci A, Tutudaki M, Tsatsakis AM, Schepens P (2002) Hair analysis: Another approach for the assessment of human exposure to selected persistent organochlorine pollutants. *Chemosphere* 46:413–418. doi: 10.1016/S0045-6535(01)00065-0
- Cremlyn R. (1991) *Agrochemicals Preparation and Mode of Action*. John Wiley Sons, New York, NY
- Dalphin JC (1998) Pathologie respiratoire en milieu agricole [Respiratory pathology in the agricultural environmen. *Rev Prat* 48:1313–1318
- Damalas CA, Eleftherohorinos IG (2011) Pesticide exposure, safety issues, and risk assessment indicators. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 8:1402–1419

- Darko G, Acquah SO (2007) Levels of organochlorine pesticides residues in meat. *Int J Environ Sci Technol* 4:521–524. doi: 10.1007/BF03325989
- Davis DL, Bradlow HL, Wolff M (1993) Medical hypothesis: Xenoestrogens as preventable causes of breast cancer. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 101:372–377
- De Coster, S.; van Larebeke N (2012) Endocrine-disrupting chemicals: associated disorders and mechanisms of action. *J Environ Public Health Article ID:1–52*
- Devi NL, Qi S, Chakraborty P (2011) Passive air sampling of organochlorine pesticides in a northeastern state of India, Manipur. *J Environ Sci* 23:808–815. doi: 10.1016/S1001-0742(10)60453-6
- Dewailly É, Mulvad G, Pedersen HS (1999) Concentration of organochlorines in human brain, liver, and adipose tissue autopsy samples from Greenland. *Environ Health Perspect* 107:823–828. doi: 10.1289/ehp.99107823
- El Nemr A, Moneer AA, Khaled A, El-Sikaily A (2013) Levels, distribution, and risk assessment of organochlorines in surficial sediments of the Red Sea coast, Egypt. *Environ Monit Assess* 185:4835–4853. doi: 10.1007/s10661-012-2907-3
- Encyclopedia of Earth (2015) Toxicology. In: *Enycl. Earth*, 14. december. <http://www.eoearth.org/topics/view/51cbfc78f702fc2ba8129e82/>
- Flury M, Flühler H, Jury WA, Leuenberger J (1994) Susceptibility of soils to preferential flow of water: A field study. *Water Resour Res* 30:1945–1954. doi: 10.1029/94WR00871
- Fredslund SO, Bonfeld-Jørgensen EC (2012) Breast cancer in the Arctic--changes over the past decades. *Int. J. Circumpolar Health* 71:19155
- Freire C, Koifman RJ, Sarcinelli PN (2014) Association between serum levels of organochlorine pesticides and sex hormones in adults living in a heavily contaminated area in Brazil. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 217:370–378. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2013.07.012
- Gilden, R.C., Huffling, K., Sattler B (2010) Pesticides and health risks. *J Obstet Gynecol Neonatal Nurs* 39:103–110. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.200>
- Guzzella L, Poma G, De Paolis A (2011) Organic persistent toxic substances in soils, waters and sediments along an altitudinal gradient at Mt. Sagarmatha, Himalayas, Nepal. *Environ Pollut* 159:2552–2564. doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2011.06.015
- Guzzella L, Roscioli C, Viganò L (2005) Evaluation of the concentration of HCH, DDT, HCB, PCB and PAH in the sediments along the lower stretch of Hugli estuary, West Bengal, northeast India. *Environ Int* 31:523–534. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2004.10.014
- Hedley AJ, Hui LL, Kypke K (2010) Residues of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in human milk in Hong Kong. *Chemosphere* 79:259–265. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2010.01.047
- Hernández AF, Parrón T, Tsatsakis AM, et al (2013) Toxic effects of pesticide mixtures at a molecular level: Their relevance to human health. *Toxicology* 307:136–145. doi: 10.1016/j.tox.2012.06.009
- Hodgson E, Rose RL (2007) Human metabolic interactions of environmental chemicals. In: *Journal of Biochemical and Molecular Toxicology*. pp 182–186
- Hoppin JA, Tolbert PE, Holly EA (2000) Pancreatic cancer and serum organochlorine levels. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev* 9:199–205. doi: 10.1158/1055-9965.epi-05-0797
- Hoppin JA, Umbach DM, London SJ (2003) Animal production and wheeze in the Agricultural Health

- Study: interactions with atopy, asthma, and smoking. *Occup Environ Med* 60:e3. doi: 10.1136/oem.60.8.e3
- Hoppin JA, Umbach DM, London SJ (2008) Pesticides and atopic and nonatopic asthma among farm women in the agricultural health study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 177:11–18. doi: 10.1164/rccm.200706-821OC
- Jabbar A, Masud SZ, Parveen Z, Ali M (1993) Pesticide residues in cropland soils and shallow groundwater in Punjab Pakistan. *Bull Environ Contam Toxicol* 51:268–273. doi: 10.1007/BF00198891
- Jakszyn P, Goñi F, Etxeandia A (2009) Serum levels of organochlorine pesticides in healthy adults from five regions of Spain. *Chemosphere* 76:1518–1524. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2009.05.048
- Jayaraj R, Megha P, Sreedev P (2016) Review Article. Organochlorine pesticides, their toxic effects on living organisms and their fate in the environment. *Interdiscip. Toxicol.* 9:90–100
- Jeyaratnam J (1990) Acute pesticide poisoning: a major global health problem. *World Heal Stat Q* 43:139–144. doi: 10.2307/2533484
- Júnior JLR, Ré-Poppi N (2007) Determination of organochlorine pesticides in ground water samples using solid-phase microextraction by gas chromatography-electron capture detection. *Talanta* 72:1833–1841. doi: 10.1016/j.talanta.2007.02.024
- Kanthasamy A, Jin H, Anantharam V (2012) Emerging neurotoxic mechanisms in environmental factors-induced neurodegeneration. *Neurotoxicology* 33:833–837. doi: 10.1016/j.neuro.2012.01.011
- Kawakami Y, Fuke C, Fukasawa M (2017) An experimental study of postmortem decomposition of methomyl in blood. *Leg Med* 25:36–42. doi: 10.1016/j.legalmed.2017.01.001
- Kim D, Ryu H-Y, Lee JH (2013) Organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls in Korean human milk: contamination levels and infant risk assessment. *J Environ Sci Health B* 48:243–250. doi: 10.1080/03601234.2013.742413
- Kim SA, Kim KS, Lee YM (2015) Associations of organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls with total, cardiovascular, and cancer mortality in elders with differing fat mass. *Environ Res* 138:1–7. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2015.01.021
- Kleanthi G, Katerina L, Evaggelia P, Andreas L (2008) Mechanisms of Actions and Health Effects of Organochlorine Substances : a Review. *Heal Sci J* 2:89–98
- Klinčić D, Romanić SH, Sarić MM (2014) Polychlorinated biphenyls and organochlorine pesticides in human milk samples from two regions in Croatia. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol* 37:543–552. doi: 10.1016/j.etap.2014.01.009
- Kolani L, Mawussi G, Sanda K (2016) Assessment of Organochlorine Pesticide Residues in Vegetable Samples from Some Agricultural Areas in Togo. *Am J Anal Chem* 7:332–341. doi: 10.4236/ajac.2016.74031
- Koutros S, Langseth H, Grimsrud TK (2015) Prediagnostic serum organochlorine concentrations and metastatic prostate cancer: A nested case-control study in the Norwegian Janus Serum Bank Cohort. *Environ Health Perspect* 123:867–872. doi: 10.1289/ehp.1408245
- Król S, Zabiegała B, Namieśnik J (2013) Human hair as a biomarker of human exposure to persistent organic pollutants (POPs). *TrAC Trends Anal Chem* 47:84–98. doi: 10.1016/j.trac.2013.02.010
- Kumar B, Verma VK, Mishra M (2014) DDT and HCH (Organochlorine Pesticides) in Residential Soils

- and Health Assessment for Human Populations in Korba, India. *Hum Ecol Risk Assess* 20:1538–1549. doi: 10.1080/10807039.2013.858563
- Kyle PB, Smith S V., Baker RC, Kramer RE (2013) Mass spectrometric detection of CYP450 adducts following oxidative desulfuration of methyl parathion. *J Appl Toxicol* 33:644–651. doi: 10.1002/jat.1792
- Lange C, Kuch B, Metzger JW (2014) Estrogenic activity of constituents of underarm deodorants determined by E-Screen assay. *Chemosphere* 108:101–106.
- Lari SZ, Khan NA, Gandhi KN (2014) Comparison of pesticide residues in surface water and ground water of agriculture intensive areas. *J Environ Heal Sci Eng* 12:. doi: 10.1186/2052-336X-12-11
- Lee D-H, Lee I-K, Song K (2006) A strong dose-response relation between serum concentrations of persistent organic pollutants and diabetes: results from the National Health and Examination Survey 1999-2002. *Diabetes Care* 29:1638–1644. doi: 10.2337/dc06-0543
- Lee D, Jacobs DR PM (2007) Association of serum concentrations of persistent organic pollutants with the prevalence of learning disability and attention deficit disorder. *J Epidemiol Community Heal* 61:591–596.
- Lee DH, Steffes MW, Sjödin A (2011) Low dose organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls predict obesity, dyslipidemia, and insulin resistance among people free of diabetes. *PLoS One* 6:. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0015977
- Lee S, Kim S, Lee HK, et al (2013) Contamination of polychlorinated biphenyls and organochlorine pesticides in breast milk in Korea: Time-course variation, influencing factors, and exposure assessment. *Chemosphere* 93:1578–1585. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.08.011
- Letta BD, Attah LE (2013) Residue levels of organochlorine pesticides in cattle meat and organs slaughtered in selected towns in West Shoa Zone, Ethiopia. *J Environ Sci Heal - Part B Pestic Food Contam Agric Wastes* 48:23–32. doi: 10.1080/03601234.2012.693866
- Li J, Jiang S, Chang Y (2013) Association among Serum Organochlorine Pesticide Residues, Glutathione S-Transferase M1 Genetic Polymorphism and Female Breast Cancer. *Adv Breast Cancer Res* 02:19–23. doi: 10.4236/abcr.2013.22005
- Li J, Li N, Ma M, et al (2008) In vitro profiling of the endocrine disrupting potency of organochlorine pesticides. *Toxicol Lett* 183:65–71. doi: 10.1016/j.toxlet.2008.10.002
- López T, Pumarega JA, Pollack AZ (2014) Adjusting serum concentrations of organochlorine compounds by lipids and symptoms: A causal framework for the association with K-ras mutations in pancreatic cancer. *Chemosphere* 114:219–225. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.04.066
- Luminita Marutescu MCC (2017) Molecular mechanisms of pesticides toxicity
- Majewski, M.S., Capel, P.D. (1995) . *Pesticides in the Atmosphere: Distribution, Trends, and Governing Factors*. Ann Arbor Jackson Concr Form Inc
- Malik A, Ojha P, Singh KP (2009) Levels and distribution of persistent organochlorine pesticide residues in water and sediments of Gomti River (India) - A tributary of the Ganges River. *Environ Monit Assess* 148:421–435. doi: 10.1007/s10661-008-0172-2
- Margni M, Rossier D, Crettaz P, Jolliet O (2002) Life cycle impact assessment of pesticides on human health and ecosystems. *Agric Ecosyst Environ* 93:379–392. doi: 10.1016/S0167-8809(01)00336-X
- Mathur V, Bhatnagar P, Sharma RG (2002) Breast cancer incidence and exposure to pesticides among

- women originating from Jaipur. *Environ Int* 28:331–336. doi: 10.1016/S0160-4120(02)00031-4
- Matthews G. (2006) *Pesticides: Health, Safety and the Environment*. Blackwell Publ Oxford, UK
- McGlynn KA, Abnet CC, Zhang M (2006) Serum concentrations of 1,1,1-Trichloro-2,2-bis(p-chlorophenyl)ethane (DDT) and 1,1-Dichloro-2,2-bis(p-chlorophenyl)ethylene (DDE) and risk of primary liver cancer. *J Natl Cancer Inst* 98:1005–1010. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djj266
- Medehouenou, T.C.M.; Ayotte, P.; Carmichael, P.H.; Kröger, E.; Verreault, R.; Lindsay, J.; Dewailly, É.; Tyas, S.L.; Bureau, A.; Laurin D (2014) Plasma polychlorinated biphenyl and organochlorine pesticide concentrations in dementia. *Can Study Heal Aging Environ Int* 69:141–147
- Megharaj M (2002) Heavy pesticide use lowers the soil health. *Form ahead* 121:37–38
- Messaros, B.M., Rossano, M.G., Liu, G., Diamond, M.P., Friderici, K., Nummy-Jernigan K., Daly, D., Puscheck, E., Paneth N, Wirth, J.J. (2009) Negative effects of serum p,p'-DDE on sperm parameters and modification by genetic polymorphisms. *Environ Res* 109.:457–464.
- Michielsen C, Zeamari S, Leusink-Muis A (2002) The environmental pollutant hexachlorobenzene causes eosinophilic and granulomatous inflammation and in vitro airways hyperreactivity in the Brown Norway rat. *Arch Toxicol* 76:236–247. doi: 10.1007/s00204-002-0326-x
- Migliore L, Coppedè F (2009) Environmental-induced oxidative stress in neurodegenerative disorders and aging. *Mutat. Res. - Genet. Toxicol. Environ. Mutagen.* 674:73–84
- Mrema EJ, Rubino FM, Brambilla G (2013) Persistent organochlorinated pesticides and mechanisms of their toxicity. *Toxicology* 307:74–88. doi: 10.1016/j.tox.2012.11.015
- Mustafa MD, Banerjee BD, Ahmed RS (2013) Gene-environment interaction in preterm delivery with special reference to organochlorine pesticides. *Mol Hum Reprod* 19:35–42. doi: 10.1093/molehr/gas039
- Needham LL, Ozkaynak H, Whyatt RM (2005) Exposure assessment in the National Children's Study: introduction. *Env Heal Perspect* 113:1076–1082. doi: 10.1289/ehp.7613
- Nicolopoulou-Stamati P, Pitsos MA (2001) The impact of endocrine disrupters on the female reproductive system. *Hum Reprod Update* 7:323–330. doi: 10.1093/humupd/7.3.323
- Ntow WJ, Tagoe LM, Drechsel P, et al (2008) Accumulation of persistent organochlorine contaminants in milk and serum of farmers from Ghana. *Environ Res* 106:17–26. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2007.05.020
- Olsen JH, Andersen a, Dreyer L (1997) Summary of avoidable cancers in the Nordic countries. *APMIS Suppl* 76:141–6. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0463.1997.tb05617.x
- Ornoy A, Weinstein-Fudim L, Ergaz Z (2015) Prenatal factors associated with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). *Reprod. Toxicol.* 56:155–169
- Parada, H.; Wolff, M.S.; Engel, L.S.; White, A.J.; Eng, S.M.; Cleveland, R.J.; Khankari, N.K.; Teitelbaum, S.L.; Neugut, A.; Gammon M. (2016) Organochlorine insecticides DDT and chlordane in relation to survival following breast cancer. *Int J Cancer* 138:565–575.
- Parro'n T, Requena M, Hernández AF, Alarcó'n R (2014) Environmental exposure to pesticides and cancer risk in multiple human organ systems. *Toxicol Lett* 230:157–165. doi: 10.1016/j.toxlet.2013.11.009
- Parsehian S Der (2008) Plaguicidas organoclorados en leche materna. *Rev del Hosp Matern Infant Ramón Sardá* 27:70–78
- Pearce N, Ait-Khaled N, Beasley R (2007) Worldwide trends in the prevalence of asthma symptoms: Phase III of the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC). *Thorax* 62:757–765. doi:

10.1136/thx.2006.070169

- Perera FP, Rauh V, Whyatt, RM (2005) A summary of recent findings on birth outcomes and developmental effects of prenatal ETS, PAH, and pesticide exposures. In: *NeuroToxicology*. pp 573–587
- Perry MJ (2008) Effects of environmental and occupational pesticide exposure on human sperm: A systematic review. *Hum. Reprod. Update* 14:233–242
- Phuong NTK, Hoang TT, Van PH (2017) Encouraging rational antibiotic use in childhood pneumonia: a focus on Vietnam and the Western Pacific Region. *Pneumonia* 9:7. doi: 10.1186/s41479-017-0031-4
- Physician AC of C (2014) Respiratory Diseases in the World. *Glob Reports FIRS Report: Respiratory Diseases in the World* www
- Polanco Rodríguez ÁG, Riba López MI, DelValls Casillas TÁ (2017) Monitoring of organochlorine pesticides in blood of women with uterine cervix cancer. *Environ Pollut* 220:853–862. doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2016.10.068
- Qu W, Suri RP, Bi X, Sheng G, Fu J (2010) Exposure of young mothers and newborns to organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) in Guangzhou, China. *Sci Total Environ* 408:3133–3138. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2010.04.023
- Que, H.S.S., Sutherland, R.G., Mc Kinlay, K.S., Saha JG (1975) . Factors effecting the volatility of DDT, dieldrin, and dimethylamine salt of (2,4-dichlorophenoxy) acetic acid (2,4-D) from leaf and glass surfaces. *Bull Environ Contam Toxicol* 3:284–290
- R. Q (2002) Endosulfan poisoning in Kasaragod, Kerala, India. *Rep a fact i nding Mission PAN*
- Ren A, Qiu X, Jin L, Ma J, Li Z, Zhang L, Zhu H, Finnell RH, Zhu T (2011) Association of selected persistent organic pollutants in the placenta with the risk of neural tube defects. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 108:12770–12775. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1105209108
- Roberts EM, English PB, Grether JK (2007) Maternal residence near agricultural pesticide applications and autism spectrum disorders among children in the California Central Valley. *Environ Health Perspect* 115:1482–1489. doi: 10.1289/ehp.10168
- Rodríguez AGP, López MIR, Casillas ÁDV (2018) Impact of pesticides in karst groundwater. Review of recent trends in Yucatan, Mexico. *Groundw. Sustain. Dev.* 7:20–29
- Rosenbaum PF, Weinstock RS, Silverstone AE (2017) Metabolic syndrome is associated with exposure to organochlorine pesticides in Anniston, AL, United States. *Environ Int* 108:11–21. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2017.07.017
- Saeedi Saravi SS, Dehpour AR (2016) Potential role of organochlorine pesticides in the pathogenesis of neurodevelopmental, neurodegenerative, and neurobehavioral disorders: A review. *Life Sci* 145:255–264. doi: 10.1016/j.lfs.2015.11.006
- Saeedi Saravi SS, Shokrzadeh M (2014) Effects of washing, peeling, storage, and fermentation on residue contents of carbaryl and mancozeb in cucumbers grown in greenhouses. *Toxicol Ind Health* 32:1135–1142. doi: 10.1177/0748233714552295
- Sagiv SK, Thurston SW, Bellinger DC, Tolbert PE, Altshul LM, Korrick SA (2010) Prenatal organochlorine exposure and behaviors associated with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder in school-aged children. *Am J Epidemiol* 171:593–601. doi: 10.1093/aje/kwp427
- Salehi F, Turner MC, Phillips KP, Wigle DT, Krewski D, Aronson KJ (2008) Review of the etiology of

- breast cancer with special attention to organochlorines as potential endocrine disruptors. *J. Toxicol. Environ. Heal. - Part B Crit. Rev.* 11:276–300
- Sarkar S, Bhattacharya B, Bhattacharya A, Chatterjee M, Alam A, Satpathy K (2008) Occurrence, distribution and possible sources of organochlorine pesticide residues in tropical coastal environment of India: an overview. *Environ Int* 34:1062–71
- Sarwar M (2015) The Dangers of Pesticides Associated with Public Health and Preventing of the Risks. *Int J Bioinforma Biomed Eng* 1:130–136
- Sharma BM, Bharat GK, Tayal S, Nizzetto L, Čupr P, Larssen T (2014) Environment and human exposure to persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in India: A systematic review of recent and historical data. *Environ. Int.* 66:48–64
- Sharma T, Banerjee BD, Mazumdar D, et al (2015) Association of organochlorine pesticides and risk of epithelial ovarian cancer: A case control study. *J Reprod Heal Med* 1:76–82. doi: 10.1016/j.jrh.2015.01.006
- Shokrzadeh M, Saeedi Saravi SS (2009) The investigation and measurement of residues of benomyl and mancozeb pesticides in shrub and nonshrub cucumbers sampled from different regions of Mazandaran province (Iran). *Electron J Environ Agric Food Chem* 8:174–178. doi: 10.1080/02772240802389910
- Shokrzadeh M, Saravi SSS (2009) Pesticides - Formulations, Effects, Fate. In: *Pesticides in Agricultural Products: Analysis, Reduction, Prevention.* pp 225–242
- Simeonov LI, Macaev FZ, Simeonova BG (2013) Environmental Security Assessment and Management of Obsolete Pesticides in Southeast Europe. *NATO Sci Peace Secur Ser C Environ Secur* 134:. doi: 10.1007/978-94-007-6461-3
- Sinaii N, Cleary SD, Ballweg ML, Niewman LK SP (2002) High rates of autoimmune and endocrine disorders, i bromyalgia, chronic fatigue syndrome and atopic disease among women with endometriosis. *A Surv Anal Hum Reprod* 17:2715–2724
- Smith-Spangler C, Brandeau ML, Hunter GE, et al (2012) Are organic foods safer or healthier than conventional alternatives?: A systematic review. *Ann. Intern. Med.* 157:348–366
- Song L, Zhao J, Jin X, Li Z, Newton IP, Liu W, Xiao H ZM (2014) The organochlorine p,p'-dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane induces colorectal cancer growth through Wnt/beta-catenin signalling. *Toxicol Lett* 229:284–291.
- State L (2011) Organophosphate and Carbamate Pesticide Residues in. *J Innov Res Eng Sci* 2:50–61
- Stewart BW, Wild CP (2014) World cancer report 2014. *World Heal Organ* 1–2. doi: 9283204298
- Sudaryanto A, Kunisue T, Kajiwara N, Iwata H, Adibroto TA, Hartono P, Tanabe S (2006) Specific accumulation of organochlorines in human breast milk from Indonesia: Levels, distribution, accumulation kinetics and infant health risk. *Environ Pollut* 139:107–117. doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2005.04.028
- Swackhamer DL, Hites RA (1988) Occurrence and bioaccumulation of organochlorine compounds in fishes from siskiwit lake, isle royale, lake superior. *Environ Sci Technol* 22:543–548. doi: 10.1021/es00170a010
- Syed JH, Malik RN, Liu D, Xu Y, Wang Y, Li J, Zhang G, Jones KC (2013) Organochlorine pesticides in air and soil and estimated air-soil exchange in Punjab, Pakistan. *Sci Total Environ* 444:491–497. doi:

10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.12.018

- Tariq MI, Afzal S, Hussain I SN (2007) Pesticides exposure in Pakistan: a review. *Environ Int* 33:1107–22
- Tariq MI, Afzal S, Hussain I (2006) Degradation and persistence of cotton pesticides in sandy loam soils from Punjab, Pakistan. *Environ Res* 100:184–196. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2005.05.002
- Tariq MI, Afzal S, Hussain I (2004) Pesticides in shallow groundwater of Bahawalnagar, Muzafargarh, D.G. Khan and Rajan Pur districts of Punjab, Pakistan. *Environ Int* 30:471–479. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2003.09.008
- Torres-Sánchez L, Schnaas L, Cebrián ME, del Carmen Hernández M, Valencia EO, Hernández R.M.G, López-Carrillo L (2009) Prenatal dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene (DDE) exposure and neurodevelopment: A follow-up from 12 to 30 months of age. *Neurotoxicology* 30:1162–1165. doi: 10.1016/j.neuro.2009.08.010
- Tsang HL, Wu S, Leung CK, Tao S, Wong MH (2011) Body burden of POPs of Hong Kong residents, based on human milk, maternal and cord serum. *Environ Int* 37:142–151. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2010.08.010>
- Sharma T, Banerjee BD, Mazumdar D, Tyagi, V, Thakur G, Guleria K, Tripathi A K (2015) Association of organochlorine pesticides and risk of epithelial ovarian cancer: A case control study. *J Reprod Heal Med* 1:76–82
- U.S. Geological Survey (1995) Pesticides in groundwater. US Geol Surv Fact Sheet FS, p. 244–295.
- Wassermann M, Nogueira DP, Tomatis L, Mirra AP, Shibata H, Arie G, Cucos S, Wassermann D (1976) Organochlorine compounds in neoplastic and adjacent apparently normal breast tissue. *Bull Environ Contam Toxicol* 15:478–484. doi: 10.1007/BF01685076
- Wilson WW, Shapiro LP, Bradner JM, Caudle WM (2014) Developmental exposure to the organochlorine insecticide endosulfan damages the nigrostriatal dopamine system in male offspring. *Neurotoxicology* 44:279–287. doi: 10.1016/j.neuro.2014.07.008
- Wolf MS, Toniolo PG, Lee EW, Rivera M DN (1993) Blood levels of organochlorine residues and risk of breast cancer. *J Natl Cancer Inst* 21:648–52.
- Wong LI, Labrecque MP, Ibuki N, Cox ME, Elliott JE, Beischlag TV (2015) P,p'-Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (p,p'-DDT) and p,p'-dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene (p,p'-DDE) repress prostate specific antigen levels in human prostate cancer cell lines. *Chem Biol Interact* 230:40–49. doi: 10.1016/j.cbi.2015.02.002
- World Health Organization (2010) The Who Recommended Classification of Pesticides By Hazard and Guidelines To Classification 2009. World Heal Organ 1–60. doi: ISBN 978 92 4 154796 3
- Yadav D, Mittal P, Agarwal H P (1981) . Organochlorine insecticide residues in soil and earth- worms in the Delhi area, India, August–October. *Pestic Monit Journal* 15:80–5
- Yadav IC, Devi NL, Syed JH, Cheng Z, Li J, Zhang G, Jones KC (2015) Current status of persistent organic pesticides residues in air, water, and soil, and their possible effect on neighboring countries: A comprehensive review of India. *Sci Total Environ* 511:123–137. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.12.041
- Yang JZ, Wang ZX, Ma LH, Shen XB, Sun Y, Hu DW, Sun LX (2015) The organochlorine pesticides residues in the invasive ductal breast cancer patients. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol* 40:698–703. doi: 10.1016/j.etap.2015.07.007

- Yates SR, Wang D, Papiernik SK, Gan J (2002) Predicting pesticide volatilization from soils. *Environmetrics* 13:569–578. doi: 10.1002/env.542
- Yu Y, Li C, Zhang X, Zhang X, Pang Y, Zhang S, Fu J (2012) Route-specific daily uptake of organochlorine pesticides in food, dust, and air by Shanghai residents, China. *Environ Int* 50:31–37. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2012.09.007
- Yu Y, Wang B, Wang X, Wang R, Wang W, Shen G, Shen H, Li W, Wong M, Liu W, Tao S (2013) Hexachlorocyclohexanes (HCHs) in placenta and umbilical cord blood and dietary intake for women in Beijing, China. *Environ Pollut* 179:75–80. doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2013.03.056
- Zala SM, Penn DJ (2004) Abnormal behaviours induced by chemical pollution: A review of the evidence and new challenges. *Anim. Behav.* 68:649–664
- Zhang G, Chakraborty P, Li J, Sampathkumar P, Balasubramanian T, Kathiresan K, Takahashi S, Subramanian A, Tanabe S, Jones KC (2008) Passive atmospheric sampling of organochlorine pesticides, polychlorinated biphenyls, and polybrominated diphenyl ethers in urban, rural, and wetland sites along the coastal length of India. *Environ Sci Technol* 42:8218–8223. doi: 10.1021/es8016667
- Zhang J, Huang Y, Wang X, Lin K, Wu K (2015) Environmental polychlorinated biphenyl exposure and breast cancer risk: A meta-Analysis of observational studies. *PLoS One* 10:. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0142513
- Zhang W, Jiang F, Ou J (2011) Global pesticide consumption and pollution : with China as a focus. *Proc Int Acad Ecol Environ Sci* 1:125–144. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.0000/issn-2220-8860-piaees-2011-v1-0012>

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the National Key R&D Program of China (2017YFD0200400); the Key R&D Program of Zhejiang Province (2018C02032); the National Natural Science Foundation of China (31570387; 31901885); the Zhejiang Provincial Natural Science Foundation of China (LQ18C140003).

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure and data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

